

Title: How storytelling can boost Analytics

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INTRODUCTION:

Companies from different industries involved somehow in the world of Data Science & Big Data Analytics, while consolidating their huge amount of data into some kind of data visualization faces complex issues and struggle to tell an efficient story to clients, we will walk through techniques to make this process easier.

AIM:

To show some techniques in terms of data visualization to best present and utilize in the day to day to facilitate the interpretation from client side.

ABSTRACT:

A massive growth in data is occurring day after day in real world and data scientists are even busier consolidating this data to a high and efficient standard of visualization, inspired by creative techniques and great stories to put together all this content that does not take to a failed approach to clients. Companies from different industries involved somehow in the world of Data Science & Big Data Analytics, while consolidating their huge amount of data into some kind of data visualization faces complex issues and struggle to tell an efficient story to clients, we will walk through techniques to make this process easier.

To be successful while presenting insights to clients, it is necessary to add value to their businesses and show them the power of going deep in data and impact by touching on the right business problem.

- Sketching your data before building a dashboard
- Choosing the right KPIs for clients
- Defining a start point to tell your story
- Evaluating impact for business
- Testing the best visualization
- Combining storytelling and data visualizations

Clients are also even more rigorous and demanding in terms of useful, quickly, and understandable dashboards. Given the methodology to best define your approach to customers it can facilitate and make the life from customers easier while interpreting different KPIs and data visualizations as well as boosting your business in terms of data analytics.

CONCLUSIONS:

Clients are also even more rigorous and demanding in terms of useful, quickly, and understandable dashboards. Given the methodology to best define your approach to customers it can facilitate and make the life from customers easier while interpreting different KPIs and data visualizations as well as boosting your business in terms of data analytics.

KEYWORDS:

Data Visualization; Dashboard; Business Problem, Storytelling, Analytics

BIOGRAPHY:

Gustavo Andrade Banhara has a diploma in Project Management (IBAT College Dublin - Ireland), a B.Sc in Computer Science and a partial MBA in Business Intelligence from universities in Brazil. He worked across multiple renowned companies such as Unisys, EY, HSBC, Santander Group and ABNAMRO supporting Data Analytics, Data Management, Business Intelligence mainly in the financial and retail sector.